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This paper must be cited as:

B.V. Padlyak, I.I. Kindrat, V.T. Adamiv, A. Drzewiecki, I. Stefaniuk, Spectroscopic properties and photoluminescence of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass, Mater. Res. Bull. 175 (2024) 112788, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.materresbull.2024.112788>.

Spectroscopic properties and photoluminescence of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass

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Abstract. High quality glasses with $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ composition, containing 1.0 mol.% MnO_2 and Sm_2O_3 impurities were obtained and studied by XRD, EPR and optical spectroscopy methods. Local structure parameters (interatomic distances and coordination numbers) were derived from XRD analysis. Analysis of EPR and optical spectroscopy (absorption, luminescence excitation, emission, decay kinetics) data shows the presence of $\text{Mn}^{2+}(3d^5)$ and $\text{Mn}^{3+}(3d^4)$ ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass. Particularly, in network of the studied glass are identified three types of the Mn^{2+} centres: single Mn^{2+} (1) centres in the strongly distorted sites (ratio of rhombic and axial constants $|E/D| \leq 1/3$), single Mn^{2+} (2) centres in the sites with almost cubic symmetry ($D \cong 0$ and $E \cong 0$), and Mn^{2+} pair centres and their small clusters, coupled by magnetic dipolar and exchange interactions. The EPR spectra parameters of Mn^{2+} centres, observed in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass, were determined at $T = 295$ K. Optical absorption spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass consists of a very broad and intense band peaked at 467 nm belonging to the ${}^5\text{E}_g(\text{D}) \rightarrow {}^5\text{T}_{2g}(\text{D})$ transition of Mn^{3+} ions and several weak narrow lines of the $\text{Sm}^{3+}(4f^5, {}^6\text{H}_{5/2})$ ions belonging to the ${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{P}_{3/2}$ visible and ${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{F}_{9/2}$, ${}^6\text{F}_{7/2}$, and ${}^6\text{F}_{5/2}$, infrared transitions. Emission spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass exhibits a broad band corresponding to the ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{G}) \rightarrow {}^6\text{A}_{1g}(\text{S})$ transition of Mn^{2+} ions and three characteristic bands in yellow-orange-red range corresponding to the ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{5/2}$, ${}^6\text{H}_{7/2}$, and ${}^6\text{H}_{9/2}$ transitions of Sm^{3+} ions. Photoluminescence (excitation and emission) spectra as well as decay kinetics of Mn^{2+} and Sm^{3+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass were discussed in comparison with corresponding results for $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glasses. The $\text{Sm}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Mn}^{2+}$ energy transfer in the studied glass is discussed.

Keywords: $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass; XRD; EPR; optical absorption; photoluminescence; decay kinetics; energy transfer.

1. Introduction

At present time, the study of borate glasses represents significant practical interest due to their attractive physical, optical and especially luminescent properties [1–7]. This interest is caused with simple and inexpensive producing technology of borate glasses in comparison with their crystalline analogues as well as their good thermal stability, high transparency in a wide spectral range, and possibility of doping by transition metal (TM) and rare-earth (RE) elements in a wide concentration range. Absorption and emission spectra of TM ions show broad bands corresponding to $d-d$ electronic transitions between energy states created by crystal field splitting. Spectroscopic properties of TM ions are strongly influenced by the coordination environment provided by ligands. Absorption and emission spectra of RE ions show narrow bands corresponding to $f-f$ electronic transitions between energy levels created by spin-orbit splitting. The wavelength position of these transitions is weakly host dependent. Both RE and TM luminescent ions can undergo energy transfer processes with other RE and/or TM ions.

Attractive and unique spectroscopic properties and high luminescence quantum yield of the TM and RE ions in oxide materials allow their widespread applications in lighting, phosphors, optical filters, lasers, and scintillators [8,9]. In particular, the un-doped and doped with TM and RE elements borate compounds represent very promising materials for detectors and transformers of ionizing radiation as well for scintillators and thermoluminescent dosimeters of different kinds of radiation and elementary particles [10–13], including neutrons [14–16]. Thus, perspectives of wide applications of borate crystals and glasses, doped with TM and RE elements stimulate synthesis of new boron-containing optical materials and intensive study of their spectroscopic and luminescent properties.

The manganese dioxide (MnO_2) was used in this work for doping of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass. Manganese (Mn) belongs to chemical elements of the TM group and characterised by an electron configuration $3d^5 4s^2$. The oxidation state of manganese can vary depending on the specific compound in which it is incorporated. For example, it ranges from +2 in the MnO to +7 in the KMnO_4 . Typically, when manganese occurs as an impurity in oxide compounds, its most common

oxidation states are +2 ($3d^5$), +3 ($3d^4$), and +4 ($3d^3$). The coexistence of Mn^{2+} and Mn^{3+} ions in Mn-doped oxide glasses is well documented in the literature [17–19]. The Mn^{2+} ions are detected by EPR and luminescence spectroscopy, whereas the Mn^{3+} ions are detected by optical absorption [17–19]. Thus, optical (absorption and luminescence) and EPR spectroscopy are two important techniques for studying the electronic properties of manganese ions in different compounds. By studying the optical absorption spectrum, it is possible to obtain valuable information regarding the electronic transitions occurring between the ground state and various excited states, while the luminescence emission spectrum provides valuable information about the relaxation mechanisms from the excited states to the ground state. The EPR spectroscopy allows to identify unpaired electrons in the ion and accurately determine their spin state, providing valuable information about the ion's electronic and local (coordination environment) structure. The combination of optical (absorption and luminescence) and EPR spectroscopy techniques offers a more complete understanding of manganese ions' properties in the structure of different materials.

It should be noted that Mn-doped borate compounds are interesting materials for radiation dosimetry. In its pure form, lithium tetraborate ($Li_2B_4O_7$) is not a very efficient for radiation dosimetry. However, when it is doped with Mn, the trapping of charge carriers (electrons and holes) generated by the incident radiation increases significantly and the intensity of the recombination luminescence during readout also increases. As a result, Mn-doped lithium tetraborate ($Li_2B_4O_7:Mn$) is a well-known thermoluminescent dosimeter (TLD) material [20–22]. Readout of dosimeters based on the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn$ is relatively simple and can be performed using standard thermally stimulated luminescence (TSL) or optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) techniques. The $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn$ dosimetry material has very good sensitivity for detecting not only of X-rays, gamma rays, and beta particles, but also fast and thermal neutrons. The $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn$ compound is inexpensive, has excellent human tissue equivalent properties and can be obtained in powder, ceramic, transparent glass, and single crystal forms. A small deviation of the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn$ dosimeter response from linearity at extremely high radiation doses is not a problem and can be resolved by calibration. Overall, the combination of high sensitivity and tissue equivalent response makes the

$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn}$ material a popular choice for medical and personal dosimetry, environmental monitoring, and industrial applications.

The samarium oxide (Sm_2O_3) was used for co-doping of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn}$ glass. The samarium (Sm) belongs to chemical elements of the RE group and characterised by an electron configuration $4f^6 6s^2$. Typically Sm is incorporated into oxide compounds as Sm^{3+} ($4f^5$) ions, which exhibit transitions within the unfilled $4f$ electron shell. The spectral characteristics of Sm^{3+} ions depend on the energy levels and transitions involved in the absorption and/or emission process. The most intense transitions in the Sm^{3+} luminescence are associated with the $^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow ^6\text{H}_J$ ($J = 5/2, 7/2, 9/2$) electronic transitions located in the yellow, orange, and red spectral regions, respectively. These transitions are very intense and therefore Sm^{3+} -doped luminescent materials are used as phosphors in solid-state lighting systems and as gain media in solid-state lasers [8,9].

One can notice that borate glasses are a suitable matrix for incorporation of the Sm^{3+} ions. The advantages of using borate glasses as a host matrix for Sm^{3+} doping include good chemical stability and relatively simple preparation technology. It is pertinent to mention that the luminescent characteristics of borate glasses doped with Sm^{3+} ions have attracted considerable attention from researchers and have been extensively published in research articles during last time [23–29]. In particular, luminescent properties of the Sm-doped borate glasses with different basic compositions ($\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$, LiKB_4O_7 , CaB_4O_7 , and LiCaBO_3) and different Sm_2O_3 impurity concentrations have been detailed studied in a number of our works [26–28]. Attractive results were obtained for the Sm-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass exhibiting highest luminescence quantum yield among the investigated borate glasses [28]. A further enhancement of the Sm^{3+} luminescence in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm},\text{Ag}$ glass in comparison with the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass was reported in our article [29]. Increasing of the Sm^{3+} external quantum yield of luminescence in 1.43 times in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm},\text{Ag}$ glass was explained by the excitation energy transfer from Ag^+ ions and small molecule-like silver nanoclusters to the Sm^{3+} ions [29]. Thus, co-doping of the Sm-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass with other RE and/or TM elements may be useful for better excitation of the Sm^{3+} luminescence and increasing of the light output. Further research is needed in this area.

The combination of spectroscopic properties of Mn and Sm impurity ions can lead to interesting spectroscopic behaviours. By co-doping a host material with both Mn and Sm impurities, colour tuning of the emitted light can be achieved. Energy transfer from Mn to Sm or vice versa can affect the luminescence properties of a co-doped material, leading to increased emission intensity and its efficiency. Thus, combination of spectroscopic properties of Mn and Sm impurities offers valuable insights for both scientific understanding and practical applications.

Detailed studies of materials co-doped with Mn and Sm have been scarce in the literature up to the present time. In particular, the effects of Sm and Mn co-doping on the structural and magnetic properties of BiFeO₃ multiferroic films have been studied in [30]. The luminescence properties of CdSiO₃:Mn²⁺,RE³⁺ (RE = Sm, Dy, Eu) long-lasting phosphors have been reported in [31]. Photoluminescence spectrum of the CdSiO₃:Mn²⁺,Sm³⁺ phosphor under excitation at 286 nm shows a narrow Sm³⁺ band peaked at 600 nm and a broad Mn²⁺ band peaked at 587 nm [31]. The Sm³⁺ and Mn²⁺ co-doped CdSiO₃ phosphor shows a longer afterglow decay time than the Mn²⁺-doped phosphor [31]. The effects of Sm co-doping on luminescent properties of Sr₄Al₁₄O₂₅:M (M = Mn⁴⁺, Cr³⁺) phosphors have been studied in [32]. Co-doping with Sm³⁺ ions decreased the emission intensity of the ²E → ⁴A₂ transition of Mn⁴⁺ ions at 651 nm in the Sr₄Al₁₄O₂₅:Mn⁴⁺,Sm³⁺ phosphor [32]. Tunable emission of the Sm³⁺ and Mn²⁺ co-doped CaZn₂P₂O₈ phosphor in spectral range of 500 – 750 nm was reported in [33]. Photoluminescence spectrum of the Ca_{0.94}Zn_{1.97}P₂O₈:0.06Sm³⁺,0.03Mn²⁺ phosphor under excitation at 400 nm includes a broad band at 552 nm corresponding to the ⁴T₁ → ⁶A₁ transition of Mn²⁺ ions and four narrow bands, which were assigned to the ⁴G_{5/2} → ⁶H_{5/2}, ⁶H_{7/2}, ⁶H_{9/2}, and ⁶H_{11/2} transitions of Sm³⁺ ions [33]. The effect of Sm³⁺ and Mn²⁺ incorporation on the structure and luminescence properties of Zn₂SiO₄ phosphor has been investigated in [34]. The Zn₂SiO₄:2.0%Sm,*x*%Mn (*x* = 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, and 4.0) phosphors under excitation at 396 nm show four main emission bands at 564 nm, 600 nm, 648 nm, 706 nm, which were assigned to the 4*f* – 4*f* transitions of Sm³⁺ ions and an emission band at 584 nm, assigned to the ⁴T₁ → ⁶A₁ transition of Mn²⁺ ions [34]. The highest intensity of Mn²⁺ luminescence was observed in the 1.0 mol.% Mn²⁺ doped Zn₂SiO₄ sample [34].

Based on the presented above short review we can state that spectroscopic properties of the Mn-Sm co-doped glasses are poorly studied at present time. Moreover, studies of the Mn and Sm co-doped materials reported in the literature were focused on phosphors, whereas the influence of Mn impurity on the spectroscopic properties of Sm^{3+} ions in borate glasses is not detailed investigated up to now. For that reason, the main aim of this article is detailed investigation the effect of Mn and Sm co-doping on the local structure, spectroscopic, and luminescence properties of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass. The XRD, EPR, optical absorption, and photoluminescence (emission, excitation, and decay kinetics) techniques were used by us for this purpose.

2. Experimental details

2.1. Synthesis of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass and samples preparation

The $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass of high chemical purity and optical quality was obtained by the standard melt-quenching technology of the borate glass, described firstly in [35]. For obtaining of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass were used Li_2CO_3 compound and boric acid (H_3BO_3). The Mn and Sm impurities were added to the raw materials as MnO_2 dioxide and Sm_2O_3 oxide, respectively, in amounts of 1.0 mol.%. The raw materials in the stoichiometric proportion were thoroughly mixed, placed into a corundum ceramic crucible, and then the obtained mixture was put in an electric furnace for melting process. Entire process of the studied glass preparation was realised in the air. Samples of the Mn-Sm co-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass were made by rapid cooling of the corresponding melt. Technological process of obtaining of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass can be presented by the following multi-step chemical reaction:

Obtained $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass samples were prepared for registration of optical absorption, photoluminescence emission and excitation spectra as well as decay kinetics by cutting and

polishing them to a size of $12 \times 8 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$. The glass samples with an approximate size of $3 \times 2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ were used for investigations by XRD and EPR techniques.

2.2. Experimental methods and equipment

The XRD pattern of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass was registered with usage computer-controlled DRON-3 X-ray diffractometer and Cu $K\alpha$ -radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). The paramagnetic centres in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn}$ glass were investigated using multifrequency and multiresonance EPR spectrometer “BRUKER” of the FT-EPR ELEXSYS Series E 580 – 10/12, operated in the X-band (work frequency $\nu \cong 9.845260 \text{ GHz}$) at room temperature ($T = 295 \text{ K}$) and in the $4.2 - 100 \text{ K}$ temperature range with usage of helium flow cryostat.

Optical absorption spectra were registered at $T = 295 \text{ K}$ using the UV-2600 Shimadzu spectrophotometer equipped with the ISR-2600Plus two-detector integrating sphere attachment. The spectrophotometer includes double beam photometric system, halogen and deuterium lamps, and a single diffraction grating. Measurement range of the spectrophotometer with ISR-2600Plus attachment is $220 - 1400 \text{ nm}$. The photoluminescence emission and excitation spectra as well as the emission decay curves were recorded at $T = 295 \text{ K}$ with usage a FluoroMax-4P Horiba spectrofluorimeter. The spectrofluorimeter is equipped with a 150 W xenon lamp, two (excitation and emission) grating monochromators and photomultiplier tube of the R928P type.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. XRD investigation of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass

Typical experimental XRD data for studied $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ samples as a function of the modulus of scattering vector $s = 4\pi \sin \theta / \lambda$ (where θ is scattering angle, $\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) are presented in Fig. 1 by black circles. The smoothed XRD pattern without narrow crystalline peaks that is presented by red curve in Fig. 1 confirms disordered glassy (or vitreous) structure of the studied sample. Relative narrow peak near 18 nm^{-1} in the experimental XRD profile corresponds to a small amount of the SiO_2 polycrystalline compound from the crucible in which the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass

was melted (see reference XRD data for SiO₂ crystal, presented by magenta line in Fig. 1). It is worth noting that the main observed maxima in the intensity profile of the Li₂B₄O₇:Mn,Sm glass closely match the positions and intensities of the main reference peaks for the Li₂B₄O₇ crystal, which are presented by blue line in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The experimental XRD data (black circles) and smoothed XRD curve (red line) for studied Li₂B₄O₇:Mn,Sm glass as well as referenced data for Li₂B₄O₇ crystal (blue line) and SiO₂ crystal (magenta line) as functions of the modulus of scattering vector s .

Registered XRD curve was analysed in order to get information about the local structure of the Li₂B₄O₇:Mn,Sm glass, including interatomic distances and coordination numbers. The intensity of scattered radiation, $I(s)$, of a system of atoms can be written as follows:

$$I(s) = NF^2(s) \left\{ 1 + \int_0^{\infty} 4\pi r^2 [\rho(r) - \rho_0] \frac{\sin sr}{sr} ds \right\}, \quad (2)$$

where $s = 4\pi \sin\theta/\lambda$ is the modulus of scattering vector, N is the number of atoms, $F^2(s)$ is the atomic structure factor, r is the distance, $\rho(r)$ is the atomic density, ρ_0 is the average atomic density.

Using the Fourier transformation of the Eq. (2) was obtained the radial distribution function (RDF) in the following form:

$$4\pi r^2 \rho(r) = 4\pi r^2 \rho_0 + \frac{2r}{\pi} \cdot \int_{s_1}^{s_2} s \left[\frac{I(s)}{NF^2(s)} - 1 \right] \sin(sr) ds . \quad (3)$$

The radial distribution function $4\pi r^2 \rho(r)$ describes the variation of atomic density in dependence of distance r .

Fig. 2. Calculated radial distribution function with indicating decomposed correlations for some pairs of atoms of the first, second, third, and other more distant ones coordination spheres of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass network.

In Fig. 2 is presented calculated radial distribution function and its decomposition on the partial binary radial distribution functions with denoted average interatomic distances for certain atom pairs in the first, second, third, and other more distant ones coordination spheres of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass network. It is important to note that the partial binary radial distribution functions with maxima at 0.255, 0.345, and 0.519 nm correspond to the superposition of the (Li-O) and (O-O), (B-B) and (O-O), (Li-O) and (O-O) atom pairs, respectively. The average interatomic distances indicated in Fig. 2 for pairs of atoms in the second, third, and other more distant coordination spheres are hypothetical and have not been detailed analysed in this article. Therefore, in Table 1 are given only the average distances between neighbouring atoms and the number of

atoms surrounding a given atom in the first coordination sphere of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass network. Presented in Table 1 coordination numbers for B and Li atoms in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass were evaluated by integrating of the corresponding bands in the radial distribution function (Fig. 2). For comparison in Table 1 also are presented the corresponding average interatomic distances ($r_{\text{B-O}}$, $r_{\text{Li-O}}$) and coordination numbers ($N_{\text{B-O}}$, $N_{\text{Li-O}}$) in the network of un-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass [35] as well as the precise distances ($r_{\text{B-O}}$, $r_{\text{Li-O}}$), average distances ($r_{\text{B-O}}^{\text{av}}$), and coordination numbers ($N_{\text{B-O}}$, $N_{\text{Li-O}}$) in the lattice of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ crystal [36].

Table 1. Average B–O distances ($r_{\text{B-O}}$) and coordination numbers to oxygen for B ($N_{\text{B-O}}$) as well as average Li–O distances ($r_{\text{Li-O}}$) and coordination numbers to oxygen for Li ($N_{\text{Li-O}}$) in the studied $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass, which were derived from the radial distribution function (Fig. 2). The experimental errors and calculating uncertainties for the obtained average interatomic distances and coordination numbers are ± 0.003 nm and ± 0.3 , respectively.

Glass composition	$r_{\text{B-O}}$ [nm]	$N_{\text{B-O}}$	$r_{\text{Li-O}}$ [nm]	$N_{\text{Li-O}}$
$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass (this article)	0.161	3.0 4.0	0.255	4.9
$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Eu}$ glass [37]	0.157	3.0 4.0	0.255	4.7
$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass [35]	0.165	3.5	0.279	4.4
$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ crystal [36]	0.1355;0.1371; 0.1374; $r_{\text{B-O}}^{\text{av}} = 0.1367$ 0.1453;0.1506; 0.1502;0.1454; $r_{\text{B-O}}^{\text{av}} = 0.1479$	3.0 4.0	0.2061	4.0

Note. In Table 1 for comparison with the studied $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass are given the relevant structural parameters (interatomic distances and coordination numbers) for $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Eu}$ glass and un-doped glass and a crystal with the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ basic composition.

Based on the results of XRD analysis (see Fig. 2 and Table 1) it is possible to state that the BO_3 triangles and BO_4 tetrahedra are the main glass-forming units in the structural network of the

$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass. The Li atoms predominantly belong to the modifiers of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass structure with the coordination number of $N_{\text{Li-O}} \cong 4 - 7$. Obtained structural results for $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass show satisfactory agreement with the corresponding results for un-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass [35] and crystal [36] as well as for $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Eu}$ glass [37]. Particularly, the obtained in this work structural results show that the local structure of the studied $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass, un-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass [35], $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ crystal [36], and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Eu}$ glass [37] is closely similar. But, the BO_3 and BO_4 glass-forming units as well as the LiO_n ($n = 4 - 7$) modifiers in the network of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$, $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Eu}$ [37], and un-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ [35] glasses are more distorted and are characterised by significantly larger average interatomic distances than the corresponding distances in the lattice of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ crystal.

3.2. EPR spectroscopy of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass

The X-band EPR spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass, registered in wide (a) and narrow (b) magnetic field scan ranges at room temperature ($T = 295$ K), are presented in Fig. 3. The observed EPR spectrum in a wide magnetic field range consists of a broad band, denoted as $\text{Mn}^{2+}(1)$, a sharp line, denoted as $\text{Fe}^{3+}(1)$, and an intense broad band, denoted as $\text{Mn}^{2+}(2)$ (see Fig. 3 (a)). The $\text{Mn}^{2+}(2)$ EPR signal is best observed in a narrow magnetic field scan range (see Fig. 3 (b)) and contains six weakly-resolved hyperfine components, caused by the nuclei of ^{55}Mn isotope (natural abundance – 100%, nuclear spin $I = 5/2$). It should be noted that the EPR signals, denoted as $\text{Mn}^{2+}(1)$ and $\text{Mn}^{2+}(2)$ in Fig. 3 were observed in a number of oxide glasses with different composition, doped with Mn and belong to the Mn^{2+} ($^6\text{S}_{5/2}, 3d^5$) ions [37–43]. Parameters of the Mn^{2+} EPR signals in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass have been determined at $T = 295$ K. For $\text{Mn}^{2+}(1)$ centres were obtained the following parameters: isotropic g -factor $g_{\text{iso}} = 4.29 \pm 0.01$ and peak-to-peak derivative linewidth $\Delta H_{\text{pp}}(1) \cong 470$ Gs with un-resolved hyperfine structure. For $\text{Mn}^{2+}(2)$ centres were obtained the following parameters: isotropic g -factor $g_{\text{iso}} = 2.01 \pm 0.01$, peak-to-peak derivative linewidth $\Delta H_{\text{pp}}(2) \cong 500$ Gs with weakly-resolved six-component hyperfine structure,

caused by nuclei of ^{55}Mn isotope, average value of the hyperfine interaction constant $A_{\text{av}} = (89 \pm 3)$ Gs, and peak-to-peak derivative linewidth of the hyperfine component $\Delta H_{\text{pp}} \cong 70$ Gs.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. The X-band EPR spectrum of the Li₂B₄O₇:Mn,Sm glass, registered in wide (a) and narrow (b) magnetic field ranges at T = 295 K.

Above is given the average value of the hyperfine interaction constant $A_{av} = (89 \pm 3)$ Gs for Mn^{2+} (2) centres, because the splitting between hyperfine components is essentially non-equidistant and equals about 71 Gs for first and second components and about 109 Gs for fifth and sixth components. The essential non-equidistance of the hyperfine components for Mn^{2+} (2) centres is caused by influence of the zero-field splitting parameters D (axial crystal field term) and E (orthorhombic crystal field term), which lead to appearance of the fine structure in EPR spectra of crystals. It should be noted that the local structure symmetry and zero-field splitting parameters (D and E) for $3d^5$ -ions (Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+}) in oxide glasses are a subject of the controversial discussions in scientific literature up to now.

According to interpretation, given in [37–43], we can state that the isolated Mn^{2+} centres in the $Li_2B_4O_7$ glass network occupy strongly distorted sites of rhombic local symmetry where ratio $|E/D| \leq 1/3$ that leads to appearance of the Mn^{2+} (1) EPR signal with $g \cong 4.3$ and sites with nearly cubic local symmetry ($D \cong 0, E \cong 0$) that leads to observation of the Mn^{2+} (2) EPR signal with $g \cong 2.0$. Different kinds of possible fully rhombic distortions (ratio $|E/D| = 1/3$) of the octahedral and tetrahedral sites in glasses were considered in [39]. The absence of hyperfine structure of the ^{55}Mn isotope nuclei for Mn^{2+} (1) centres is caused by a wide distribution of the zero-field splitting parameters (D and E) in the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ glass network.

Beside the Mn^{2+} (1) and Mn^{2+} (2) EPR signals in the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ glass is observed a broad ($\Delta H_{pp} \cong 500$ Gs) unresolved underlying response centred at $g = 2.0$ (see Fig. 3), which according to [38,40,42] can be attributed to the $Mn^{2+} - Mn^{2+}$ pair centres coupled by magnetic dipolar interaction and exchange coupled Mn^{2+} pairs and clusters. Thus, the Mn is incorporated into the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ glass network as isolated Mn^{2+} ions in the strongly distorted (Mn^{2+} (1) centres) and nearly cubic (Mn^{2+} (2) centres) octahedral or/and tetrahedral sites as well as dipolar and exchange coupled Mn^{2+} pairs and small manganese clusters.

The Sm impurity can be incorporated into the structure of oxide compounds as paramagnetic Sm^{3+} ($4f^5, {}^6H_{5/2}$) non-S-state Kramers ions or Sm^{2+} ($4f^6, {}^7F_0$) non-paramagnetic ions. The Sm^{3+} and Sm^{2+} ions can be identified by EPR and optical (absorption and luminescence) spectroscopy. It

should be noted that up to present time the EPR spectra of Sm^{3+} and other rare-earth non-S-state Kramers ions in disordered solids, including glasses are studied insufficiently. The X-band EPR spectra of other non-S-state Kramers rare-earth ions (Ce^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Dy^{3+} , Er^{3+} , Yb^{3+}) in network of zeolites according to [44] consist of extremely broad asymmetric signals, which can be clearly observed at liquid helium temperatures only. The reference data on EPR spectroscopy of the Sm^{3+} ions in zeolites are absent [44]. The EPR spectra at liquid helium temperatures of the Sm^{3+} ions in tetraborate glasses with $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ and $\text{CaB}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ composition containing 0.5 and 1.0 mol.% Sm_2O_3 firstly were published in our article [28].

The X-band EPR spectra of the studied $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass, registered in the 6 – 100 K temperature range, are presented in Fig. 4.

As we can see from Fig. 4 in the 6 – 20 K temperature range clearly observed a new extremely broad asymmetric EPR signal with $g_{\text{eff}} \cong 9.7$ that is closely similar to the EPR signal, observed in the 4.2 – 20 K temperature range in $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass containing 0.5 mol.% of the Sm_2O_3 impurity [28].

Fig. 4. The X-band EPR spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass, registered in the 6 – 100 K temperature range.

This EPR signal is associated with isolated Sm^{3+} centres in disordered $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass network. The EPR signal of isolated Sm^{3+} centres disappears above $T = 20$ K (see Fig. 4 and Ref. [28]) due to shortening of their spin-lattice relaxation time. Therefore, the EPR spectroscopy at liquid helium temperatures clearly demonstrates presence of the Sm^{3+} isolated centres in the investigated $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass. Characteristic optical absorption and photoluminescence spectra of the non-paramagnetic Sm^{2+} ($4f^6$, 7F_0) ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass are not observed (see *Subsections 3.3, 3.4, and 3.5*). Thus, according to EPR and optical spectroscopy data one can conclude that the samarium impurity is incorporated into the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass network as non-S-state Kramers Sm^{3+} ($4f^5$, $^6H_{5/2}$) paramagnetic ions, exclusively.

In addition to the characteristic EPR signals of the Mn^{2+} and Sm^{3+} ions, the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass also exhibits single-line EPR signals with effective isotropic g -factors of $g_{\text{iso}} \cong 4.29$ and $g_{\text{iso}} \cong 2.00$, denoted as $\text{Fe}^{3+}(1)$ and $\text{Fe}^{3+}(2)$ (see Fig. 3 (a)) and $\text{Fe}^{3+}(1)$ (see Fig. 4), respectively. These signals according to [38–40,45] are associated with Fe^{3+} ($3d^5$, $^6S_{5/2}$) paramagnetic ions of the non-controlled iron impurity. The Fe^{3+} EPR signals, observed in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass, are similar to signals, which were observed previously by us and other authors in oxide glasses with different basic compositions [28,37–40,45–50]. Presence of the Fe^{3+} EPR signal with $g_{\text{iso}} \cong 4.29$ clearly indicates classical glass structure of the studied $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ compound that also was supported by XRD data analysis in the *Subsection 3.1*. It should be noted that the concentration of the Fe^{3+} impurity in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass is relatively low, and its weak forbidden absorption bands do not reveal in the optical absorption spectra, which are described below.

3.3. Optical absorption of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass

Optical absorption spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass is given in Fig. 5. In addition to the fundamental absorption edge, which is characterised by a strong increase of absorbance from 370 to 300 nm, can be seen a broad asymmetric band covering the spectral range of 380 – 1000 nm with a peak at 467 nm (21413 cm^{-1}). It is worth to discuss the origin of this optical absorption band.

Fig. 5. Optical absorption spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass at room temperature ($T = 295$ K).

The observed broad absorption band cannot be attributed to the Mn^{2+} ions with a $3d^5$ electron configuration. The high-spin and low-spin configurations of d^5 ions exhibit multiple absorption bands. Optical transitions in the high-spin d^5 configuration occur from the ground state $^6\text{A}_{1g}(\text{S})$ to several excited crystal field states with a multiplicity of 4, resulting in low intensity absorption bands due to spin-forbidden transitions. The low-spin d^5 configuration gives intense absorption bands originating from spin-allowed transitions between the ground state $^2\text{T}_{2g}(\text{I})$ and excited crystal field states with a multiplicity of 2. The observed single absorption band also cannot be attributed to Mn^{4+} ions with a $3d^3$ electron configuration, because optical absorption of the Mn^{4+} ions is characterised by three intense spin-allowed transitions occurring from the ground state $^4\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ to the excited crystal field states $^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$, $^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$, and $^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$.

The ground ^5D term of Mn^{3+} ions in the high-spin $3d^4$ electron configuration undergoes splitting into two crystal field states: $^5\text{E}_g$ and $^5\text{T}_{2g}$. No other crystal field states with a multiplicity of 5 are present. Consequently, Mn^{3+} ions in the high-spin configuration reveal a single absorption

band. On the other hand, Mn^{3+} ions in the low-spin configuration reveal numerous intense absorption bands arising from spin-allowed transitions between the ground state ${}^3T_{1g}(H)$ and excited crystal field states with a multiplicity of 3.

Therefore, the broad absorption band at 467 nm is assigned to the spin-allowed transition between the ${}^5E_g(D)$ and ${}^5T_{2g}(D)$ states of Mn^{3+} ions in the high-spin $3d^4$ electron configuration. Observed optical absorption band well agrees with previously published results of spectroscopic studies on Mn-doped oxide glasses [41,43,51]. Notably, a similar broad absorption band with a maximum around 470 nm has been reported in Mn-doped lithium borate [51], lead lithium borate [41], and lead aluminium borate [43] glasses.

It should be noted that distortion of octahedral (O_h group) crystal field often occurs in glass network, leading to creation of elongated or shortened structural octahedra (D_{4h} group). This distortion leads to splitting of the 5E_g state into ${}^5B_{1g}$ and ${}^5A_{1g}$ levels, and splitting of the ${}^5T_{2g}$ state into ${}^5B_{2g}$ and 5E_g levels. Consequently, the asymmetric shape of the observed absorption band (see Fig. 5) can be caused by the superposition of three transitions related to elongated and/or shortened oxygen octahedra in the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ glass.

Optical absorption spectrum of the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ glass reveals also weaker narrow bands at 401 nm, 1075 nm, 1223 nm, and 1367 nm (see the inset of Fig. 5). These bands are attributed to the Sm^{3+} ions ($4f^5$ electron configuration) and correspond to the ${}^6H_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6P_{3/2}$, ${}^6H_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6F_{9/2}$, ${}^6H_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6F_{7/2}$, and ${}^6H_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6F_{5/2}$ transitions, respectively. Due to the overlap between the narrow absorption band of Sm^{3+} ions at 401 nm and the strong broad absorption of Mn^{3+} ions, there is an opportunity to enhance the excitation efficiency of the $4f - 4f$ transitions of Sm^{3+} ions. Consequently, the possibility of the $Mn^{3+} \rightarrow Sm^{3+}$ energy transfer requires investigation by luminescence techniques, which are presented below.

3.4. Luminescence of the Sm^{3+} ions in $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ and $Li_2B_4O_7:Sm$ glasses

Luminescence emission spectra of the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ and $Li_2B_4O_7:Sm$ glasses are given in Fig. 6. Three intense and two weak emission bands corresponding to the ${}^4G_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_J$ ($J = 5/2, 7/2,$

9/2, 11/2, 13/2) transitions of the Sm^{3+} ions are observed in spectral range of 540 – 820 nm (see Fig. 6). Most intense Sm^{3+} emission band is peaked at 598 nm and corresponds to the ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{7/2}$ transition.

Fig. 6. Luminescence emission spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ (a) and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ (b) glasses, registered at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 401$ nm and $T = 295$ K.

The $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glasses show similar emission band profiles, but there are slight variations in the intensities of these bands. The emission bands corresponding to the ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{9/2}$, ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{11/2}$, and ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{13/2}$ transitions are stronger in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass in comparison with the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass. The intensity of the ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{7/2}$ transition is similar in both glasses. The $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass shows the lower intensity of the ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{5/2}$ transition than the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass. Table 2 presents the branching ratios of the Sm^{3+} luminescence in the investigated glasses. The dissimilarity in branching ratios can be caused by the strong and broad absorption of Mn^{3+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass. The absorption band of Mn^{3+} ions, which peaks at 467 nm and extends up to 1000 nm, results in the absorption of a portion of the Sm^{3+}

emission by the Mn^{3+} ions. The absorption of Mn^{3+} ions in the red spectral range is weaker than in the yellow-orange spectral range. As a result, an enhanced intensity of the ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{9/2}$, ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{11/2}$, and ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{13/2}$ transitions is observed in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass in comparison with the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass (see Fig. 6). Besides this, co-doping with Mn causes increasing of the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the Sm^{3+} emission bands (see Table 2). Broadening of emission bands can be caused by higher structural disorder in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass in comparison to the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass.

Table 2. The peak position (λ_{max}), full width at half maximum (FWHM) and experimental branching ratio (β) of the Sm^{3+} emission bands in $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glasses.

Transition	$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$			$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ [29]		
	λ_{max} [nm]	FWHM [cm^{-1}]	β	λ_{max} [nm]	FWHM [cm^{-1}]	β
${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{5/2}$	562	337	0.083	562	289	0.210
${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{7/2}$	598	378	0.490	598	281	0.549
${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{9/2}$	645	324	0.359	645	271	0.218
${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{11/2}$	705	578	0.062	705	553	0.022
${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{13/2}$	790	694	0.006	790	680	0.001

Luminescence excitation spectra of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glasses are given in Fig. 7. Numerous narrow excitation bands observed in Fig. 7 are attributed to the $4f - 4f$ transitions of Sm^{3+} ions. All excitation bands are identified in Fig. 7. Among observed transitions, the strongest excitation band at 401 nm corresponds to the ${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{P}_{3/2}$ transition. It is worth noting that the excitation spectrum (Fig. 7) demonstrates a higher resolution and a larger number of Sm^{3+} bands in comparison to the optical absorption spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass, presented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 7. Luminescence excitation spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ (a) and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ (b) glasses registered at $\lambda_{\text{mon}} = 598 \text{ nm}$ and $T = 295 \text{ K}$.

The decreasing of the Sm^{3+} luminescence in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass under excitation in the spectral range of $450 - 500 \text{ nm}$ can be due to the strong absorption of Mn^{3+} ions. As a result, a part of photons is absorbed by Mn^{3+} ions in the sample before excitation of Sm^{3+} ions. The absorption of Mn^{3+} ions is weaker in the spectral range of $330 - 380 \text{ nm}$ and under this excitation it is possible to observe the enhancement of the Sm^{3+} luminescence in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass in comparison with the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass (see Fig. 7). The absence of a broad asymmetric absorption band of Mn^{3+} ions in the luminescence excitation spectrum in Fig. 7 indicates the lack of $\text{Mn}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Sm}^{3+}$ energy transfer in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass.

3.5. Luminescence of the Mn^{2+} ions in $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass

Luminescence emission spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass registered under excitation at 413 nm is given in Fig. 8. A prominent feature of this spectrum is the presence of a broad emission

band extending from 520 nm to 820 nm, accompanied by five well-defined narrow emission bands, which correspond to the ${}^4G_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_J$ ($J = 5/2, 7/2, 9/2, 11/2, 13/2$) transitions of the Sm^{3+} ions. In our opinion, broad band with a maximum around 624 nm originates from the ${}^4T_{1g}(G) \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}(S)$ transition of Mn^{2+} ($3d^5$) ions. It should be noted that the position of Mn^{2+} luminescence is sensitive to local environment of the Mn^{2+} ions in a glass network. The Mn^{2+} ions in tetrahedral crystal field emit predominantly in the green spectral range, whereas the Mn^{2+} ions in octahedral crystal field emit in the red spectral range [52,53]. The observed broad emission band centred around 624 nm suggests that Mn^{2+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass network are localised in distorted octahedrally-coordinated sites.

Fig. 8. Luminescence emission spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass registered at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 413$ nm and $T = 295$ K.

Luminescence excitation spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass registered under monitoring at 624 nm is given in Fig. 9. It can be seen not only the strong excitation bands of Sm^{3+} ions but also two bands associated with Mn^{2+} ions. These excitation bands of Mn^{2+} luminescence are indicated by

arrows in Fig. 9. Based on the splitting of Mn^{2+} terms in the octahedral crystal field, it can be proposed that observed excitation bands near 413 nm and 430 nm belong to the ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}, {}^4E_g(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ transitions, respectively. These transitions were not evident in the optical absorption spectrum (see Fig. 5) due to the presence of an intense and broad absorption band of the Mn^{3+} ions, which overshadows the spin-forbidden absorption bands of the Mn^{2+} ions.

The emission and excitation bands of Mn^{2+} ions in the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ glass demonstrate a close similarity in wavelength position to those reported in [18,54,55] for oxide glasses with different compositions. The observation of strong Sm^{3+} excitation bands during the monitoring of Mn^{2+} luminescence indicates the energy transfer from Sm^{3+} to Mn^{2+} in the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ glass.

Fig. 9. Luminescence excitation spectrum of the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ glass registered at $\lambda_{mon} = 624$ nm and $T = 295$ K.

Let's return for a moment to the Mn^{3+} ions, which exhibit the strong and broad absorption band (see Fig. 5). However, despite efforts to detect Mn^{3+} luminescence, all attempts were unsuccessful. The lack of Mn^{3+} luminescence is attributed to the non-radiative transitions of Mn^{3+} ions from the

excited ${}^5T_{2g}(D)$ state to the ground ${}^5E_g(D)$ state in the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ glass.

Fig. 10. The CIE chromaticity diagram of the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ (■, ●) and $Li_2B_4O_7:Sm$ (◆) glasses.

The CIE chromaticity diagram of the investigated glasses is presented in Fig. 10. Symbols “■” and “◆” show the emission colour of the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ and $Li_2B_4O_7:Sm$ glasses under excitation at 401 nm. Symbol “●” shows the emission colour of the $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ glass under excitation at 413 nm. The emitted light from the investigated glasses belongs to the orange-red spectral range.

3.6. Luminescence decay kinetics of the Sm^{3+} and Mn^{2+} ions

Luminescence decay kinetics of the Sm^{3+} ions in $Li_2B_4O_7:Mn,Sm$ and $Li_2B_4O_7:Sm$ glasses are given in Fig. 11. The decay curves are not perfectly monoexponential. The mean lifetime (τ_{mean}) was calculated using the following formula:

$$\tau_{\text{mean}} = \frac{\int tI(t)dt}{\int I(t)dt}, \quad (4)$$

where $I(t)$ represents the luminescence intensity, while t represents the time. Obtained values of τ_{mean} equal 2.33 ms for the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass and 2.64 ms for the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass. Incorporating of Mn as a co-dopant causes a decrease of the Sm^{3+} lifetime in 12%. This effect is related to energy transfer from Sm^{3+} ions to both, Mn^{3+} and Mn^{2+} ions. A more comprehensive discussion of energy transfer channels is presented below.

Fig. 11. Luminescence decay kinetics of the Sm^{3+} ions in $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ (a) and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ (b) glasses at $T = 295$ K.

Luminescence decay kinetics of Mn^{2+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass is given in Fig. 12. The decay curve is strongly non-monoexponential, but it can be well fitted by a biexponential function with lifetimes of $\tau_1 = 1.88$ ms and $\tau_2 = 9.40$ ms. Fractions of the lifetime amplitudes are very similar to be equal 51% and 49% for τ_1 and τ_2 , respectively. The amplitude-weighted average lifetime (τ_{avg}) was calculated using the following formula:

$$\tau_{\text{avg}} = \frac{A_1\tau_1 + A_2\tau_2}{A_1 + A_2}, \quad (5)$$

where A_1 and A_2 are the amplitudes of the corresponding lifetimes. Calculated τ_{avg} equals 5.60 ms in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass that is slightly more than 5.3 ms in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn}$ glass [56]. Thus, a slight prolongation of the Mn^{2+} lifetime is observed in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass in comparison with the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn}$ glass.

Fig. 12. Luminescence decay kinetics of Mn^{2+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass at $T = 295$ K.

Shortened of the Sm^{3+} lifetime and prolonged of the Mn^{2+} lifetime together with the presence of intense Sm^{3+} transitions in the excitation spectrum of Mn^{2+} luminescence suggest the $\text{Sm}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Mn}^{2+}$ energy transfer in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass. Besides this, it is worth noting the presence of energy transfer from both Sm^{3+} and Mn^{2+} ions to Mn^{3+} ions. These channels were proposed because the emission of both Sm^{3+} and Mn^{2+} ions overlaps with the intense broad absorption of Mn^{3+} ions. The Mn^{3+} ions did not show luminescence and underwent non-radiative relaxation from the excited state to the ground state. The proposed energy transfer channels are illustrated in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13. The energy level diagram of Sm^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , and Mn^{3+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass illustrating optical transitions and energy transfer channels.

4. Conclusions

Detailed structural, EPR, and optical-luminescent investigations of the obtained glass with $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ composition, containing 1.0 mol.% MnO_2 and Sm_2O_3 show the presented below results.

- The local structure parameters (interatomic distances and coordination numbers) for $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass were derived from radial distribution function analysis and compared with other borate glasses and crystal with the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ basic composition.
- The EPR spectra of the Mn^{2+} , Sm^{3+} , and Fe^{3+} paramagnetic ions were observed in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn,Sm}$ glass at room and liquid helium temperatures and their parameters were determined and analysed in comparison with corresponding EPR spectra, observed in other glasses.

- Optical absorption spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass exhibits a strong broad band ascribed to the ${}^5\text{E}_g(\text{D}) \rightarrow {}^5\text{T}_{2g}(\text{D})$ transition of Mn^{3+} ions and several weaker narrow bands ascribed to the ${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{P}_{3/2}$, ${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{F}_{9/2}$, ${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{F}_{7/2}$, and ${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{F}_{5/2}$ transitions of Sm^{3+} ions.
- Luminescence emission spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Mn},\text{Sm}$ glass exhibit three intense and two weak emission bands ascribed to the ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_J$ ($J = 5/2 - 13/2$) transitions of the Sm^{3+} ions and a single emission band assigned to the ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{G}) \rightarrow {}^6\text{A}_{1g}(\text{S})$ transition of the Mn^{2+} ions. Emission of both Sm^{3+} and Mn^{2+} ions occurs in the orange-red spectral range, and their lifetimes lie in the millisecond range.
- The energy transfer channels $\text{Sm}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Mn}^{2+}$, $\text{Sm}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Mn}^{3+}$, and $\text{Mn}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Mn}^{3+}$ were subjected to discussion.

Acknowledgements

This research paper was supported by the Vlokh Institute of Physical Optics (Lviv, Ukraine) in the framework of scientific project No. 0122U001833 of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. One of us (I.K.) is supported by the National Science Centre (NCN) Poland within the “Miniatura” project No. DEC-2023/07/X/ST3/00737. The authors would like to thank Dr Y.O. Kulyk from the Faculty of Physics of the Ivan Franko National University of Lviv for realization of XRD measurements.

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